

“GENERAL CHARACTERISTICS AND CLASSIFICATION OF THE TERMINOLOGY OF THE UZBEK LANGUAGE EDUCATION SYSTEM”

Makhbuba Kholikova Abdimumin kizi

Master student of Asian University of Technologies;

Karshi, Kashkaarya;

Annotatsiyatel; +998 99 6641406

e-mail: xoliqovamahbuba04@gmail.com

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ABSTRACT

This article scientifically explores the formation, general lexical-semantic characteristics, structural composition, and classification of the terminology of the Uzbek language education system. It analyzes the important role of terms in the field of education, the principles of their standardization, and their alignment with international practices. The findings serve as a theoretical basis for the further refinement of the terminology of the Uzbek language education system.

Nowadays, alongside the modernization and development of the education system in the Republic of Uzbekistan, its linguistic study has also gained significant relevance. In particular, the terminology of the education system is one of the important directions within Uzbek linguistics. In the modern education system, the existence of precise, clear, and standardized terminology is considered one of the key conditions for the advancement of science and technology. As in any scientific field, the Uzbek language education system possesses its own unique terminological apparatus, which serves the function of explaining, regulating, and interpreting all stages of the educational process.

By the term Uzbek language education system terminology, we understand a set of words or phrases connected with the specific concepts of upbringing, teaching, and the theory and practice of education. As noted above, today's Uzbek educational terminology encompasses a wide range of diverse yet interconnected compound terms.

Accordingly, when we refer to the terminology of the Uzbek language education system, we mean the totality of terms related to all areas of this system, interconnected through the concepts that define its components. Analyzing this terminology allows us to identify the presence of certain thematic groups, which we understand, following I.V. Shchadurskiy [1975] and V.N. Nikolaeva [2000], as the grouping of words based on the external relations between the objects and material phenomena they denote. It is important to note that the term thematic group is not the only accepted label for such sets of lexemes; other terms are also used to name word groups, whose composition is determined by extralinguistic factors — for example, functional groups or subject groups [Shchur 1974: 104], subject-branch groups [Shchadurskiy 1975: 48], and lexical series [Akhmanova 1960: 402], among others.

Based on this, the terminology of the Uzbek language education system can be classified into the following thematic groups:

1. Names of persons in the education system:

Names of school and preschool staff: remedial teacher, teacher of the year, nursery assistant, senior teacher, teaching assistant.

Administrative and managerial staff responsible for managing educational institutions: district supervisor, supervising teacher, departmental inspector, independent inspector, subject advisor, curriculum coordinator.

Names related to pupils and students: mature student (of age), exam proctor student, head girl, part-time student, dormitory head (in boarding schools).

2. Terminology related to the theoretical aspects of education and upbringing:

Terms in pedagogy, methodology, and psychology: history of education, educational theory, educational psychology, child psychology and related academic disciplines.

Terms for research in education, research methods, processing and interpreting data: scientific research, educational research, lesson observation, nature observation, educational experiment.

Terms for concepts in education, strategies, and methods for transmitting and acquiring knowledge, skills, and value systems: authoritarian teaching, peer tutoring, incidental learning, communicative approach, automated learning.

Terms in general, developmental, and educational psychology: visual memory, negative reinforcement, generalized reinforcement, and related sociological terms such as social distance, positive discrimination.

3. Terms related to educational content:

Terms denoting curricula and their components: curriculum, syllabus, courses, and academic subjects.

Terms for types of learning and teaching activities: speed reading, revision lesson.

Terms for assessing and evaluating students' knowledge: continuous assessment, quantitative assessment, speed test, attitude test, open book exam.

4. Organization and management of educational activities:

Terms for main stages of education: primary education, secondary education, higher education.

Terms related to the academic year and school day: academic year, occasional closure, school week, sports day, free time, extended day.

Terms for organizing the educational process, managing student behavior, and maintaining discipline: behavior modification, firm discipline, internal class attendance, attendance policy.

Terms for diplomas, certificates, and degrees: standard degree, external degree, exit certificate, terminal qualification.

Terms related to financing and budgeting educational institutions, and to scholarships, grants, and benefits for students and teachers: school allowance, allocated study funds, competitive bidding, discretionary rewards, technical assistance.

Terms for various official and unofficial, state and non-state organizations and associations within the education system: academic committee, teachers' organization, parents' association, school board.

Terms for working with parents in the education system: parent selection, parent meetings, parental guidance.

Terms related to teachers' professional development and qualification improvement: teacher development, practicum, pre-service teacher training courses, school internship.

5. Terms related to the material base of educational activities:

Terms for educational institutions and associated buildings, specifically: preschool institution terms: daycare center, play school; various schools: independent school, city academy, secure learning unit; additional and higher educational institutions: art college, medical school, modern university.

Terms for study materials and raw resources: notebook, book, workbook, e-workbook, e-textbook.

Terms for various technical equipment and teaching aids: audiovisual aids, multimedia kit, home experiment kit, educational film.

In general, when studying specialized sources on the terminology of the Uzbek language education system, we have provided examples of linguistic units and certain education-related terms to illustrate their status. The classification of Uzbek educational terminology can certainly be expanded and continued from other perspectives — this will be addressed in future research.

The terminology of the Uzbek language education system is an important scientific resource for every educator and linguist. Its development is closely linked to the emergence of new pedagogical concepts, the exchange of international experience, and national language policy. In the future, it remains an essential task to study educational terminology more systematically, compile comprehensive dictionaries, and implement them in practice.

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